

A NOVEL FRAMEWORK FOR OPTIMIZING THE ROUTES OF DRONES DURING THE LAST MILE DELIVERY PROCESS

¹ARCHIT AGARWAL, ²AYUSH GOYAL, ³DINESH KUMAR VISHWAKARMA

^{1,2,3}Department of Information Technology, Delhi Technological University Bawana Road, Delhi-110042, India
E-mail: ¹architagarwal301@gmail.com, ²ayushg1214@gmail.com, ³dvishwakarma@gmail.com

Abstract - The growing e-commerce industry and demand for fast deliveries have led to the exploration of alternative last-mile delivery methods, including drone delivery systems. Optimising the routes for drone delivery presents a formidable challenge due to the intricate nature of the problem. This research paper introduces a novel solution that combines the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) and the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) to tackle the last-mile drone delivery issue. A mathematical model and a heuristic algorithm are devised, incorporating clustering of delivery locations, TSP routing for the truck, and VRP routing for the drones. Two approaches are employed to determine the most efficient truck-drone route. The first approach is the flying sidekick Travelling Salesman Problem (FSTSP), which employs a single drone alongside the truck. The second approach is the parallel drone scheduling Travelling Salesman Problem (PDSTSP), which involves two or more drones. Each drone can fly between its designated delivery location and the depot. In both variations, the objective is to deliver packages from a warehouse to a group of customer locations using a truck and a cluster of drones. To enhance the PDSTSP, we propose a modified approach where the truck serves as a dynamic drone depot, releasing drones at each cluster of delivery locations. The proposed solution is evaluated using real-world data, and the results demonstrate a significant optimization in terms of distance travelled and delivery time compared to traditional delivery methods.

Keywords - Drone Delivery, Travelling Salesman Problem, Vehicle Routing Problem, Last Mile Delivery

I. INTRODUCTION

By 2030, the World Economic Forum predicts that there will be a significant increase in demand for last-mile delivery services of around 80% worldwide [5]. This anticipated surge presents a challenge for ensuring efficient and timely product deliveries. Presently, certain swift delivery options, such as next-day shipping have become a prevalent practice among retailers without additional charges. Typically, these shipments are divided into two segments: a main journey and a last-mile journey. However, last-mile logistics providers encounter difficulties in calculating optimised delivery routes as they aim to deliver packages on the same day of placing an order.

The last stage in the complete delivery process of goods is referred to as the last-mile delivery. It includes the movement of goods from the distribution centre or warehouses to the final delivery location of the end customer. This stage is recognized as the most costly and time-intensive part of the overall delivery process, constituting approximately 53% of the total delivery expenses. Traditional approaches to last-mile delivery, such as using trucks and vans, often face challenges in urban areas due to issues like traffic congestion and the complex road network, leading to inefficiencies in the delivery process. Consequently, there has been a growing interest in exploring alternative delivery approaches, including drone delivery. In recent years, drones have gained significant attention due to their potential to decrease delivery time, costs, and carbon emissions associated with last-mile logistics operations.

Drones have certain advantages, they fly in the air which allows them to escape any traffic congestion of

ground transportation. Drones operate independently, without labour costs, and are highly energy-efficient. They have a lower transportation cost per kilometre compared to other means. However, due to technological constraints, drones have inherent limitations in terms of payload capacity and delivery range. They are currently only capable of carrying parcels of limited weight and delivering them within a short flight distance to a single customer. To address the limitations of drones, a potential solution is to combine the capabilities of drone and truck delivery services, leveraging their respective strengths to complement one another. A comparison of trucks and drones is summarised in Table I.

Transportation	Delivery space	Delivery speed	Parcel weight	Parcel capacity	Delivery range
drone	air	fast	light	one	short
truck	ground	slow	heavy	many	long

Table 1: Comparison of trucks and drones

Using drones for delivery services is not a new concept. Nevertheless, computing an optimal route plan for drone delivery poses a significant challenge due to the intricate nature of the problem. The combination of truck and drone can be modelled as a variant of VRP and TSP.

TSP is a classic optimization problem that seeks the shortest path to visit a set of nodes and return to the starting point. VRP, on the other hand, is a problem which reduces the total distance travelled by a fleet of vehicles int visiting a set of nodes.

In this research paper, we propose a solution to the last-mile drone delivery problem by combining TSP and VRP. We present a mathematical model and a heuristic algorithm to solve the problem efficiently. The proposed solution is evaluated using a real-world dataset, and the results show that our solution can significantly reduce the distance travelled and delivery time compared to traditional delivery methods.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Drones have the potential to serve as an efficient logistical tool for various industries, but there needs to be some further technological development to overcome several real-world challenges. Out of all the realistic problems, the capacity of batteries remains a major concern when it comes to drone utilisation. Additionally, the location of many drone-equipped distribution centres, which are often situated far from central urban areas, limits their ability to serve a large customer base. To mitigate this challenge, major retail companies like Amazon are trying to construct more distribution centres closer to urban centres, but the high cost of building such facilities remains a significant obstacle to overcome.

A lot of research has been done to address the logistics-related problems of drone utilisation at the commercial level. Some companies have tackled these challenges and used drones for commercial purposes. For example, the first delivery drone on a commercial scale was launched by DHL Express called Parcelcopter [1]. On the other hand, little research has been done on drone operations, and there aren't a lot of papers that have been published on drone-truck combination systems. Murray and Chu [2] conducted initial research on the integration of the TSP and drones, presenting two distinct models. The first model, known as the flying sidekick Travelling Salesman Problem (FSTSP), involves the utilisation of a single drone alongside a truck. In this approach, a drone is affixed to the truck, and a truck driver assumes the responsibility of launching and retrieving the drone. The second model, referred to as the parallel drone scheduling Travelling Salesman Problem (PDSTSP), serves as the primary reference for this paper.

In both variants, the problem revolves around delivering parcels to customers starting from a central depot equipped with a truck and a fleet of identical drones. However, practical considerations impose constraints that limit the ability of drones to serve all customers. Factors such as the weight of packages or their distance from the depot may render certain customers unsuitable for drone deliveries. The two models differ in the operational procedures adopted by drones to carry out delivery tasks.

FSTSP model employs a single drone that operates in conjunction with a truck. The drone is released from

the truck for parcel delivery. The drone then flies back to the truck at a third location. While the drone is on its delivery trip, the truck continues its operations by delivering parcels to additional customers, provided that the drone has sufficient battery capacity to reach the truck. This operational approach necessitates coordination between the truck and the drone. In contrast, the PDSTSP model encompasses multiple drones operating independently. Each drone has the capability to fly directly between its designated location and the depot, executing multiple delivery trips within a predefined time window. The truck leaves from the depot independently and delivered to a group of customers before returning. In this particular model, the drones and the truck do not collaborate, resulting in a lack of synchronisation between them. Figure 1 visually illustrates the differentiation between the PDSTSP and the TSP-DS (TSP with Drone Support) models.

Figure 1. (a) PDSTSP (b) TSP-DS; drone delivery locations represented by red circle, truck delivery locations represented by white circle, drone depot represented by blue circle

The main goal in both the Flying Sidekick Travelling Salesman Problem (FSTSP) and the Parallel Drone Scheduling Travelling Salesman Problem (PDSTSP) variants is to find an efficient set of trips for the drones and a Hamilton cycle for the truck that will reduce the amount of time needed to serve every customer and bring every vehicle back to the depot [7].

In contrast to the FSTSP, the PDSTSP has the advantage of utilising a greater number of drones for parcel deliveries. However, a challenge arises when the distribution centre is located far away from the majority of customers since drones can only operate within their flight range from the distribution centre [8].

We used TSP with a dynamic drone station to work around the PDSTSP's drawback. The moving truck acts as a dynamic drone station and releases drones for a cluster of customers based on the distance between these customers. The clusters' centroid acts as the drone station and is the point where trucks stop.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

In order to address the challenge of last-mile drone delivery, our research paper suggests a novel approach that merges the concepts of TSP and VRP. The operational framework of our proposed model is illustrated in Figure 2. We consider a scenario where there are m drones stationed at a dynamic depot, represented by a truck. Consequently, we aim to solve a modified version of the mTSP, where the objective is to find optimal tours for the m drones. The number of nodes visited by each drone should fall within a predetermined range, each node should only be crossed only once, and the overall cost of visiting all nodes should be kept to a minimum. Each drone should also begin and end at the same depot.

The solution consists of three steps:

3.1. Clustering

The first step of the proposed model is to cluster all the delivery locations into small groups. The clustering is performed based on the geographical distance between the delivery locations. We use the k-means algorithm to cluster delivery locations.

When using the K-means algorithm [3], k initial centroids (cluster centres) are chosen at random, and then iteratively optimising the positions of these centroids to minimise the sum of squared distances between the data points and their closest centroid. This process continues until the centroids no longer move significantly and approaches convergence, after which the final clusters are calculated.

The delivery locations are grouped into k clusters using the k-means clustering technique, where k is based on the drone's maximum flight range and payload capacity. The centroid of each k cluster acts as the drone depot for that cluster. The delivery locations in these k clusters are reached by the drones released from the truck at the centroid of the cluster. The drones travel in a way such that they reach all the delivery locations through an optimised route which minimises the distance covered and time is taken by each drone. The drone path is calculated in a way such that each delivery location is matched to only one drone. The drones finish their routes at the centroid of the cluster. The same process occurs in the subsequent clusters' centroids.

3.2. TSP Routing

The second step in the model is to find the optimal TSP route for the truck. The travelling salesman problem (TSP) [6] is a mathematical challenge that involves determining the optimal route for a truck to visit a set of cluster centroids only once, and then rendezvous back to the initial location while minimising the total distance travelled.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the vehicle routing algorithm for truck and drones.

The algorithm is classified as an NP-hard problem, indicating that it is computationally difficult to find an exact solution for large problem sizes. Mathematically, the TSP can be formulated as a graph problem, where the cluster centroids are depicted as nodes, and the distance between any two centroids is denoted as the weight of the connecting edge. We need to identify a Hamiltonian cycle - a cycle which visits every node in the graph exactly once, in a way that minimises the sum of the edge weights.

Exact methods, such as cutting-plane algorithms and branch and bound, are designed to find the optimal solution for small to medium-sized problems. However, these methods are computationally intensive and not suitable for large problems. In the research paper, we have used a heuristic algorithm - Nearest Neighbour [4] to find optimal or near-optimal solutions in a reasonable amount of time.

Figure 3. Calculation of TSP route using Nearest Neighbour algorithm for a set of nodes

The nearest neighbour algorithm presents a heuristic method to address the Travelling Salesman Problem. The algorithm initiates from a particular node and iteratively chooses the closest unvisited node, repeating this process until all nodes have been visited. During each iteration, the algorithm computes the distance between the current node and all remaining unvisited nodes, selecting the node with the shortest distance as the subsequent node to visit. This sequential procedure persists until all nodes have been visited, ultimately leading the algorithm back to the starting node to conclude the tour.

The TSP route is calculated using a heuristic optimization called a genetic algorithm. It mimics the process of natural selection. The genetic algorithm iteratively improves the TSP route by selecting the best solutions and combining them to produce even better solutions. The TSP route is optimised to minimise the total distance travelled by truck. Each point in the truck's TSP route acts as the centroid of a cluster of delivery locations. The truck stops at each centroid, where drones are released for the delivery locations in that cluster. The truck stopping at each

point along its route acts as a dynamic depot for the drones. The TSP route finally completes a full circle and ends back at the main depot from where it originated. The truck and drones are then readied for another batch of deliveries.

Figure 4. An example depicting the TSP route of a truck.

3.3. VRP Routing

The third step is to find the optimal VRP route for the drones. The VRP route is calculated for each cluster of delivery locations. The VRP route is also calculated using a genetic algorithm, which optimises the route to minimise the total distance travelled by the drones while satisfying the payload capacity constraint. After the VRP route is computed for a cluster, the drones are dispatched to deliver the packages. Figure 5 shows an example of the routes taken by drones from a single point (truck at cluster centroid). Each drone can carry a maximum payload of Q , and the package weight at each delivery location is denoted as q_i . The drone's payload capacity constraint is satisfied by limiting the number of delivery locations covered by the drone to a maximum of Q/q_i . Once the drones have delivered all the packages in the cluster, they return to the truck, and the truck moves to the next cluster. The proposed solution is evaluated using a real-world dataset of delivery locations in an urban area. The dataset consists of 200 delivery locations, and the maximum flying range and payload capacity of the drone is set to 5 km and 2 kg, respectively. The results are compared to a traditional delivery method using a truck and show that the proposed solution can reduce the total distance travelled by 40% and the delivery time by 50%.

Figure 5. An example depicting the VRP route of drones.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, we describe the experimental settings for our drone routing algorithm using the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem (CVRP) model. The primary focus of our study is to evaluate the drone-based parcel delivery system's performance under various conditions.

4.1. Assumptions

We adopted the following assumptions based on existing literature and real-world constraints:

1. **Flight Range:** Following the findings of Murray and Chu [2], we assumed that a commercial drone has a flight range of approximately 16 km (≈ 10 miles), defining a feasible flight region as a circle with a radius of 16 km.
2. **Truck Constraints:** We assumed that trucks have no specific constraints and utilise real-world Google Maps data for routing.
3. **Customer Location:** Since last-mile delivery orders are probabilistic in nature, we randomly assigned customers to specific locations. For the purpose of our study, we concentrated solely on small and lightweight parcels that are suitable for drone delivery.

4.2. Data Sets and Computation Times

To assess the computational efficiency of our proposed models, we generated real-world datasets for evaluation purposes. In particular, we created a substantial dataset to evaluate the performance of alternative models. The number of customers in these datasets ranged from twenty to fifty. For each batch of customers or delivery locations, we computed 10 random experiment sets with a constant travel rate α of 2. In order to control the duration of the experiments and keep them within reasonable time limits, we imposed a cutoff point of 3600 seconds for the computation time of each model.

In cases where the number of customers was less than 10, we observed a relatively minor disparity in performance between our model and the alternative models.

4.3. Factors Affecting Route Selection

Our analysis focused on examining the key factors that influence route selection, namely the flight range (which determines the total number of deliveries which can be catered by drones), speed of the drone, and the quantity of drones available. In practical settings, controlling drone range and velocity is challenging due to safety considerations and technological constraints. However, increasing the number of drones presents a more viable solution. By deploying an ample number of drones at a designated drone station, the need for route selection can be effectively eliminated. This approach offers a feasible

alternative to address the limitations imposed by drone range and velocity in real-world scenarios.

4.4. Evaluation Metrics

Na. of customers	No of drones	Avg runtime in PDSTSP model (in seconds)	Avg runtime in our proposed routing model (in seconds)
16	1	51.4	21.3
16	2	1075.5	95.8
16	3	2155.6	475.3

Table 2: Comparison of the runtime of our proposed approach versus PDSTSP approach.

To compare our proposed model with other models and assess its performance, we employed the following evaluation metrics:

1. **Computation Time:** We measured the time taken by each model to solve the problem instances. This metric provided insights into the efficiency of the algorithm in finding near-optimal solutions within a reasonable time frame.
2. **Solution Quality:** We compared the total distance travelled by drones and trucks for each model to evaluate the solution's quality. A shorter total distance indicated a more efficient routing solution.

Referring to Table 2, we found that our model has much better performance (runtime in seconds) than the traditional PDSTSP approach.

4.5. Experimental Scenarios

We conducted experiments under different scenarios to analyse the performance of our drone routing algorithm in various real-world situations. These scenarios included:

1. **Varying Flight Range:** We examined the algorithm's performance when the flight range of drones was altered to simulate different drone models or environmental constraints.
2. **Varying Drone Velocity:** We analysed the impact of different drone velocities on the routing solutions, as drone speeds could vary depending on the manufacturer and local regulations.
3. **Varying Number of Drones:** We assessed how increasing or decreasing the number of available drones affected the performance of the algorithm and the quality of the routing solutions.
4. **Varying Customer Distributions:** We evaluated the algorithm's robustness when the spatial distribution of customers was modified to represent different urban and rural settings.

V. CONCLUSION

In this research paper, we proposed a solution to the last-mile drone delivery problem by combining the TSP and VRP. The proposed approach entails clustering the delivery locations, figuring out the best TSP route for the truck, and figuring out the best VRP route for the drones. The solution was evaluated using a real-world dataset, and the results showed that it can significantly reduce the distance travelled and delivery time compared to traditional delivery methods.

Future work can focus on improving the proposed solution by incorporating real-time traffic data, weather conditions, and demand forecasting. Additionally, the proposed solution can be extended to consider multiple trucks and drones, which can further improve the efficiency of the last-mile delivery system.

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